

PREPARATION OF ANTIBACTERIALS FROM ORGANO-MERCURIALS.
PART IV. SOME MERCURATED SULPHANILAMIDES

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Thirteen mercurated derivatives of sulphanilamide have been prepared. The bactericidal action of some of these against *E. Coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* have been compared with the corresponding unmercurated compounds as well as with some azo and other simple derivatives of sulphanilamide.

In part III of this series (this issue, p. 80) the study of a number of mercurated amines showed that some of these possessed satisfactory bactericidal activities. It was thought desirable to extend the study to some mercurated sulphanilamides, which do not appear to have been described in the literature. These new products have been compared with a few azo compounds of this group as well as with a few other simple products like the Iodo, silver and N¹-acetic and N¹-propionic acid derivatives (mostly known). Tables II and III give a list of compounds prepared, their melting points and their analyses and Table I gives a summary of their bactericidal action as investigated by the usual Rideal-Walker drop method using 24 hour cultures of *E. Coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* as the test organisms. The method of preparation and properties of the products are described in the experimental portion.

It will be noticed that whereas the unmercurated compounds are very weakly active *in vitro*, the mercurated products are somewhat better. They are, however, still much weaker than the compounds described in parts I-III of this series. The compounds were dissolved in dilute HCl or NaOH as required and the solution brought to a p_H 6.5-7.5, by careful neutralisation with NH_4OH or acetic acid.

TABLE I

Sr. No.	Name of compounds.	Max. effective dilution against	
		<i>E. Coli</i> .	<i>Staphylococcus</i> .
1.	Sulphanilamide ..	1 : 500	1 : 500
2.	Sulphanilamido-N ¹ -propionic acid ..	1 : 500	1 : 500
3.	" N ¹ -acetic acid ..	1 : 500	—
4.	Trichloroethylene-disulphanilamide ..	1 : 250	—
5.	2-Amino-5-carboxyazobenzene-4'-sulphanilamide ..	1 : 250	1 : 500
6.	4-Oxy-3-chloroazobenzene-4'-sulphanilamide ..	1 : 500	1 : 1250
7.	2-Oxy-5-chloroazobenzene-4'-sulphanilamide ..	1 : 500	1 : 1250
8.	4-Amino-3-carboxyazobenzene-4'-sulphanilamide ..	1 : 250	—
9.	" 2-COOH " " " ..	1 : 250	1 : 500
10.	4-Carboxy azobenzene-3'-sulphanilamide ..	1 : 250	1 : 500
11.	3- " " " " " ..	1 : 250	1 : 500
12.	2- " " " " " ..	1 : 250	1 : 500
13.	2-Oxy-5-chloroazobenzene-4'-sulphanilamide ..	1 : 1250	1 : 1250
14.	1-Amino-2-iodobenzene-4'-sulphanilamide ..	1 : 250	1 : 250
15.	1-Amino-2 : 6-diiodobenzene-4'-sulphanilamide ..	1 : 250	1 : 250
16.	Acetoxymercuri-sulphanilamide ..	1 : 500	—
17.	Benzoyloxy " " " ..	1 : 1250	1 : 1500
18.	Salicyloxy " " " ..	1 : 1250	1 : 1250
19.	Mandeloxxy " " " ..	1 : 1250	—

The mercury derivatives are fairly stable to air and light and to cold and hot water. They are unaffected by dilute NaCl and do not precipitate egg albumin in aqueous solution. The introduction of solubilising groups like N^1-CH_2COOH , or $N^1-CH_2CH_2COOH$ seems to reduce the activity. Se also does combination with chloral (compound No. 4). The azo-chlorophenol derivatives are more active than the other azo compounds. The introduction of benzoyloxy or salicyloxy group with the mercury produces some improvement on the acetoxymercuri group. On account of the poor activities of the compounds generally, the whole series were not biologically tested.

EXPERIMENTAL

The mono and di-iodo derivatives were prepared according to Scudil (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 1480). The azo compounds were prepared by diazotising sulphanilamide and coupling with aminobenzoic acids and chlorophenols or by diazotising aminobenzoic acids and coupling with sulphanilamide. The mercuri derivatives were prepared (as in the case of mercurated phenols and amines in the other parts of this series) by heating a mixture of sulphanilamide (1 mol.), HgO (1 or 2 mols.) and acetic or other organic acids (1 or 2 mols.) in water or alcohol solution on the water-bath for 1-3 hours, cooling, filtrating and crystallising from hot dilute acetic acid. They are soluble in dilute HCl and NaOH but insoluble in most organic solvents. The di-derivatives required longer heating (5 hours) for their preparation. They were purified by dissolving in dilute NaOH and precipitating with dilute acetic acid. The sulphadiazines were also mercurated in the same way. The products are very sparingly soluble in water and in organic solvents, except in hot glacial acetic acid.

For estimation of nitrogen in the mercurated products a modified Kjeldahl method was used (Bradstreet, *Chem. Rev.*, 1942, 27, 333). For the azo compounds the method suggested by Marsh (*Am. Chem. Abstr.*, 1931, 25, 5871) was used. Tables II and III give a list of the compounds, their m.p. or decomposition temperature and their analysis for N and Hg.

TABLE II

Sr. No.	Name of the compounds.	Percentage of mercury	
		Calculated.	Observed.
2.	Acetoxymercuri-sulphanilamide	46.57	45.00
3.	Diacetoxymercuri- " "	58.22	56.00
4.	Benzoyloxy- " "	40.70	40.00
5.	Dibenzoyloxy- " "	49.32	48.05
6.	Salicyloxy- " "	39.45	38.20
10.	Lactoxy- " "	43.63	43.00
8.	Mandeloxo- " "	38.46	37.15
29.	Acetoxymercuri-sulpha-pyridine	39.69	38.10
30.	" " " -thiazole	39.04	38.55
31.	" " " -diazine	39.42	39.01
26.	" " " -guanidine	42.43	44.00
27.	" " " -prontosil	36.48	35.46
28.	" " " -benzyl-sulphanilamide	38.51	35.99

TABLE III

Sr. No.	Name of the compounds.	M. p.	Percentage of nitrogen	
			Calc.	Obs.
1.	Sulphanilamide	..	..	..
2.	Acetoxy-mercuri-sulphanilamide	..	..	..
3.	Diacetoxy- " " "	245° (d)	6.50	6.61
4.	Benzoyloxy- " " "	285° (d)	4.06	3.82
5.	Dibenzoyloxy- " " "	255° (d)	5.59	5.88
6.	Salicyloxy- " " "	285-89° (d)	3.44	3.00
7.	Disalicyloxy- " " "	255° (d)	5.51	5.42
8.	Mandeloxy- " " "	271° (d)	3.32	3.45
9.	Dimandeloxy- " " "	278-83° (d)	5.36	5.18
10.	Lactoxy- " " "	294-96° ((d)	3.21	3.01
11.	Dilactoxy- " " "	230° (d)	6.08	5.70
12.	Sulphanilamido-acetic acid	288° (d)	3.74	3.10
13.	" -propionic acid	255°	12.10	11.70
14.	Trichloroethylene-di-sulphanilamide	124°	11.47	11.41
15.	Sulphanilamido-silver	98-100°	11.82	11.21
16.	2-Hydroxy-5-chloroazobenzene-4'-sulphanilamide	215° (d)	10.04	9.14
17.	4- " 8-chloroazobenzene-4'-sulphanilamide	210° (d)	13.40	12.00
18.	2-Amino-5-carboxyazobenzene-4'-sulphanilamide	230° (d)	13.40	12.5
19.	4-Carboxyazobenzene-3'-sulphanilamide	156-58° (d)	17.5	17.0
20.	4-Amino-3-carboxyazobenzene-3'-sulphanilamide	123-25° (2)	"	18.9
21.	3-Carboxyazobenzene 3'- " "	158° (d)	"	16.95
22.	4-Amino-2-carboxy- 4'- " "	154° (d)	"	16.4
23.	2-Carboxyazobenzene, 3'- " "	150° (d)	"	17.0
24.	1-Amino-2-iodobenzene-4'- " "	160° (d)	"	17.3
25.	" 2:5-di- " 4'- " "	179°	9.30	9.20
26.	Acetoxymercuri-sulphaganidine	215°	6.60	6.42
27.	" " -prontosil	210° (d)	11.25	11.85
28.	" " benzylsulphanilamide	205-206° (d)	12.01	12.74
		170° (d)	5.30	5.37

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